

ATHEROSCLEROSIS OF CORONARY VESSELS WITH NORMAL MACRO AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE THYROID GLAND IN PRACTICALLY HEALTHY PERSONS

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Relevance

A significant role in the pathogenesis of coronary artery disease, the development of its complications and possible outcomes is played by neurohumoral regulation. Of great importance in the course of IHD is the functional thyroid condition.

Material and methods

To study the morphogenesis of atherosclerosis of the coronary arteries 80 observations were selected from practically healthy individuals who died from accidental causes and had a normal histostructure of the thyroid gland for areas of Bukhara. The vessels of the dead were studied in over 30 years of age. At the age of 30 - 39 years - 38 observations, 27 at the age of 40-49 years - 27, at the age of 50-59 years - 10, at the age of 60 years and older - 5 observations.

The pathological anatomy of coronary atherosclerosis has been studied according to the severity of the total area of atherosclerosis. The results of morphometric studies of the coronary atherosclerosis in each age group were compared with macro - and microscopic changes in the thyroid gland.

Research results

Analysis of planimetric studies showed that the dynamics atherosclerotic process in the right coronary artery repeats the general patterns established for descending branch of the left coronary artery, but differed - from it some originality. Thus, in the 3rd decade first and second stage atherosclerotic lesions reached a value of $1+0.2\%$. In the 4th decade atherosclerotic index reached a value of $9.9 + 1.6\%$. AT

In the 5th decade, the affected area increased by 1.3 times and atherosclerotic index reached $13.1 + 3.5\%$. in the 6th decade and older, the affected area increased by 2.6 times and atherosclerotic index reached $34.4 + 10.1\%$.

Conclusions

Thus, in the right coronary artery with age continuous progression of atherosclerosis,

however, the rate of its growth is not the same in every decade. So, in the 4th decade, the area of intima lesion atherosclerosis increased almost 10 times, in

subsequent

decades, the growth rate of the affected area is several slept and reached 1.3 in the 5th decade and 2.6 over the age 60 years.

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